

Representative learning designs: A scoping review

Chris McCosker,¹ Scott Russell,² Ian Renshaw,² Ross Pinder,³ Keith Davids⁴

¹ School of Behavioural and Health Sciences, Australian Catholic University, Brisbane, QLD, Australia

² Queensland University of Technology, Brisbane, QLD, Australia

³ Paralympic Innovation, Paralympics Australia, Adelaide, SA, Australia

⁴ Sport & Human Performance research group, Sheffield Hallam University, A119 Collegiate Hall, Collegiate Crescent, Sheffield S10 2BP, UK

Start Date

Friday 1st June, 2024

Anticipated completion date

January 1st, 2025

Stage of review at time of submission

The initial search, screening of abstracts and screening of full text articles has been completed.

Contact

Chris McCosker

chrismccosker05@gmail.com

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None

Conflict of interest

The authors have no conflicts of interest

Review Question

The purpose of this scoping review was to (1) enhance theoretical understanding and applications in practice of representative learning design (2) summarise current findings in a meaningful and practical way (3) identify gaps in the literature and (4) develop understanding to help bridge the gap between research and practice

Searches

From July 4th until July 5th, 2024 a scoping literature review following PRISMA-SCR (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analysis Protocols-Scoping Review) guidelines was performed in three electronic databases (PsychINFO, SPORTSDiscus and Web of Science) to identify journal articles that described or investigated representative learning designs using any practice, learning, experimental or competition setting in sport. All articles were written in English.

Search strategy

The following keywords were used to identify relevant records:

1. Representative learning design OR representative training design OR representative practice design OR representative design

Condition or domain being studied

Representative learning designs in sport.

Participants/population

This scoping review included articles across all sporting disciplines.

Concept

This scoping review considered articles that described or investigated the use of representative learning designs in sport.

Context

The context of this review is any practice, learning, experimental or competition setting across any sport.

Sources

This scoping review considered quantitative, qualitative and mixed methods study designs for inclusion. Resources were peer-reviewed. Unpublished and grey literature were not included in this review.

Main outcome(s)

Enhance understanding and application of representative learning design.

Data extraction (selection and coding)

One author (CM) performed the initial search, two authors screened abstracts (CM and SR) and two authors (CM and SR) reviewed the full text articles using the platform Covidence.

Risk of bias (quality) assessment

There is a small risk of bias since two authors screened abstracts for inclusion. However, since this study is exploratory, all articles deemed relevant were included.

Strategy for data synthesis

This study is focused on discussion of the topic and as such, there will not be any quantitative analyses performed.

Analysis of subgroups or subsets

None

Type and method of review

Scoping review

Dissemination plans

Publication in a peer-reviewed journal will assist in disseminating the findings of this study.

Keywords

Scoping review, representative learning design, training design

Current review status

Ongoing